

THE USE OF SHADOWING EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ORAL SPEECH IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the peculiarities of oral speech i.e. talkative and listening skills in teaching foreign languages and the use of shadowing educational technologies in the development of oral speech.

President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev said that it is necessary to popularize the study of foreign languages among the population and create the necessary conditions for their perfect assimilation, coordinate the introduction of internationally recognized programs and textbooks of teaching foreign languages at all stages of education, and develop modern teaching skills in teachers.

As N. N. Normatova states, "The process of developing the oral speech skills of foreign language for linguistic departments of Higher Education is different from the process of developing it for non-philological departments. The process has its own peculiarities. The quality of education, which is a bilateral process between the teacher and student, depends on the didactic perfection of teacher's mastery, and on the other hand, the on the student's motivational activity.

Oral speech, as an effective process, requires a lot of time and effort from the student, since it also requires the inclusion of language, speech and communicative competencies. As a type of communicative activity, it must be an integral part of each lesson.

The main purpose of teaching students a foreign language is to have basic speech structures that correspond to the threshold level of knowledge on the pan - European language competence scale. Teaching speech is based on topics that meet the real needs and interests of students in the upper secondary school.

It is important to create a positive environment to encourage student interaction. In such an environment, they can express their thoughts, feelings and thoughts without fear of making mistakes. Students can also effectively perform communicative tasks. Willis argues that creating an environment of low stress and using language for real purposes is a way to achieve meaningful communication, and through interaction, students are able to acquire

speech skills. Willis also highlights important conditions such as exposure, use, and motivation for effective language acquisition. Based on this view of language, task-based education provides many advantages in the design of communicative activities and in the development and improvement of oral speech. There are various innovative educational technologies in the development of oral speech. Currently, shadowing educational technology is one of the useful educational technologies in the development of oral speech.

Shadowing helps you develop two skills at the same time: listening and speaking. Listening to a native speaker, you will learn to distinguish between individual sounds and the features of pronouncing whole phrases. Then you repeat behind it by copying the correct accent.

It teaches "naturalness". In addition to pronunciation, the intonation and speech tempo of the carrier are imitated. This will help to better understand the flow of speech and the structure of the language.

Increases the speed of speech. Regular repetition of the same phrases and grammatical structures leads them to automatism. You don't have to remember to say "I want" in English the next time. You can say "I want" faster than the brain thinks.

The Shadowing method is not suitable for beginner level students. In order to repeat correctly after the carrier, you need to know the rules of pronunciation. Only a few can learn the language by ear from scratch. Perhaps, without prior preparation, you will not hear the difference in pronunciation.

The Shadowing technique is divided into five stages:

Blind imitation. You listen to the recording without looking at the transcript and try to understand the essence yourself. Turn the same piece several times, repeat as much as possible after the carrier.

Imitation with text. In the second step, you copy the carrier's speech, depending on the translation. Only translation! Without foreign language text. You may not read the design and grammar yet.

Shadow repeat. Imitation of the media, but the full text of his speech is in sight.

Development. You again read the text aloud, analyze all the subtleties and features of pronunciation.

Letter. At the last stage, you write the speech of the media by hand-each sentence is separate. Recorded-read aloud, recorded-read aloud. And so the whole text.

Ideally, you should practice this technique on the move, not sit down. For example, when walking. Arguelles then assures him that he will work better.

Conclusion: the importance of developing the skills of speaking and listening in teaching a foreign language and the improvement of oral speech is greatly served by the shadowing educational technology.

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